

ORGANIZING A TRANSPORT LOGISTICS SYSTEM IN PLANNING CARGO TRANSPORTATION

Kurbanov Azamat Turdalievich

Termiz State University

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Abstract: The field of logistics includes all issues related to cargo operations, from its production to final consumption. this article analyzes the organizational and regulatory issues for the establishment of logistics management of cargo delivery service processes in order to satisfy consumer needs.

Keywords: logistics, supply chain, transport, cargo delivery, consumer, raw materials.

In the conditions of current market competition, meeting the needs of consumers for transportation using the most effective technologies increases the competitiveness of the activities of transport enterprises, creates the opportunity to export transport services.

In recent years, many issues related to the transportation process have been shown to be related to logistics. Logistics as an approach to the management of the supply chain (material, information and financial flow) has become widespread in modern conditions and has attracted the attention of many scientists and practitioners [1, 9].

The field of logistics includes all issues related to cargo operations from its production (mining) to final consumption [2].

Logistics is the management of the movement of material flows, the main purpose of which is to supply the transport needs of various enterprises and organizations, and the population in the conditions of the market economy, on time, in the specified volume and assortment, with the lowest costs.

Logistics is a field of planning and control of the following material and intangible operations related to the movement of material flows, in which the following tasks are performed:

- delivery of raw materials and materials to the production enterprise;
- processing of materials and raw materials within the enterprise;
- delivery of the finished product to the consumer enterprise;
- collection, transmission, storage, processing of relevant information and finally management of these processes.

Logistics operations are an independent part of the logistics process performed from a single workplace or using a single technical device, a set of separate actions aimed at changing material and/or information flows [3].

Shipment planning is one of the most important tasks in the product distribution system. In general, planning is the process of making decisions before future actions.

The logistics system of the enterprise is one of the most complex and at the same time well-functioning mechanisms that combine various elements. The continuous operation of this mechanism is mainly determined by the precisely measured performance of each of its constituent elements, the key to which is the activity of the used components, which determines the need to study the logistics mechanism and system in every enterprise.

In the modern world, there is a rapid growth of production, expansion of enterprises, an increase in demand for warehouses, which, in turn, affects the growth of the turnover of enterprises. All this increases the role of logistics in enterprise management.

The relevance of studying the role of logistics in enterprise management is related to the process of globalization in the production and goods sector itself [5, 6], which increases the importance of logistics in any enterprise, because a significant part of costs is transportation costs. So, if the enterprise is looking for the cheapest resources outside the country in order to reduce production costs, then the share of logistics costs will increase significantly.

Based on the breadth and multidimensional nature of this problem, it is necessary to comprehensively study the tasks and goals of applying the logistics system in each individual enterprise, which is one of the urgent tasks. Logistics is an important business that opens wide opportunities for the use of human and material resources, which in turn affects the entire national production.

The market of motor transport services is related to the organization of warehouses, the formation of motor transport services in intermediary organizations. However, work in the field of logistics is not limited to these trends, it is multifaceted. Logistics work, in addition, includes management of support for the company's employees, sales activities, organization of information systems, etc. [6, 7].

The practice of large enterprises in highly developed countries in the economic field shows that logistics plays an important role in various modern business processes, their ability to compete in foreign and domestic markets is mainly determined by the development of the enterprise's logistics system and the enterprise's logistics management in general.

Logistics is a part of the enterprise supply chain process, which includes the effective planning, execution and control of its main stages, as well as the storage and movement of goods and products produced by the enterprise. In addition, the logistics system of the enterprise includes directing the flow of services and information related to the implementation of all customer requirements from the point of delivery to the end user.

A logistics chain is a technologically connected set of suppliers, consumers, carriers, intermediaries, insurers, etc. The main links in the logistics chain are as follows (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Dependence of the main links in the logistics chain

According to the principles of logistics, the organization of the production cycle system can include the rational organization of the production cycle of the enterprise, the purchase of materials and raw materials, the selection of suppliers, and the independent organization of production processes [5, 8, 9].

In order to ensure the ability of an enterprise or organization to successfully conduct business in the market, it is necessary to ensure the management of logistics material flows in accordance with the following objectives:

It should ensure the delivery of various products of the required quality to the consumers, in sufficient quantity, to the desired destination, at the required time, with minimum costs. This allows you to eliminate inventory and waiting time at the production stage, significantly reducing costs and the price of goods. As a result, the competitiveness of the product increases.

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